

Assessing Effect of Learning micro-Expressions by Analyzing Images and Video Training programs

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Abstract

Micro-expressions are reliable indicators of true emotions and therefore the ability to read them is important in many different professional areas, such as lie detection, criminal study, national security, marketing, sales and service, medical care, and law. The ability to identify micro-expressions can be enhanced with training and practice. Different tools for assessing this ability can be employed in training people to recognize micro-expressions. We conducted two studies on two different samples to examine the effectiveness of the new tool, the Micro Expressions Training Videos program, and comparing it to the Micro Expressions Training Tool. The results of the first study (n = 62) showed that scores obtained on the Micro Expressions Training Videos program correlated with the results obtained in the Micro Expressions Training Tool, which is a well-established instructional tool for micro-expression recognition. The second study (n = 2578) explored the possibility of using the Micro Expressions Training Videos program to provide training in micro-expression recognition. The results showed a systematic growth in participants' performance on Micro Expressions Training Video training tests, depending on the number completed.

Keywords: METT, METV, micro-expressions, training, micro-expression recognition

1. Introduction

Charles Darwin was the first to claim that facial expressions are universal across cultures and species (Darwin, 1872). He postulated that powerful emotions cannot be inhibited completely or fabricated accurately because of the involuntary nature of emotional expressions. Nearly a century later, Tomkins (1962, 1963) suggested that emotion was the basis of human motivation and that the seat of emotion was in the face. Building on the intercultural studies of Ekman et al. (1969) and a study conducted on the remote island of Papua New Guinea (Ekman & Friesen, 1971), Matsumoto (2001) provided strong evidence that facial expressions conveying emotions such as happiness, disgust, sadness, fear, anger, and surprise are recognized universally. Matsumoto and his colleagues concluded that facial expressions are signs of a complex response system that is common to all humans (Matsumoto, et al., 2008). Apparently, even people who are blind from birth exhibit these universally human emotional facial expressions (Cole, et al., 1989).

Haggard and Isaacs (1966) and Ekman and colleagues (Ekman, 1972, 1985, 2001, 2006; Frank & Ekman, 1997) adopted the term micro-expressions to describe extremely brief flashes of an individual's true emotions that appear uncontrollably on his or her face. These brief but salient facial expressions are associated with emotional expression. The expressions are spontaneous, produced by various brain activities, and associated with emotional reactions such as anger, compassion, and laughter. The brain processes emotional impulses that trigger involuntary muscle contractions; the resulting micro-expressions may last for up to half a second (Yan et al., 2013).

Sometimes individuals may want to suppress expressions of their true emotions or exhibit a false facial expression. In some situations, social norms compel people to conceal or alter their true feelings (Ekman, 1972). However, micro-expressions are consistent with the inhibition hypothesis (Ekman, 1988, 1991), which posits that facial expressions prevent a person from hiding their emotions. Unlike regular facial expressions, micro-expressions have the characteristic feature of being difficult to falsify, and they are perhaps impossible to conceal. Therefore, they can convey a great deal of reliable

information. Since suppressed emotions are expressed unconsciously in the form of micro-expressions, a skilled observer can use them to discern concealed feelings (Ekman & Friesen, 1969; Ekman, 2009). Ekman et al. (1992) described micro-expressions as a reflection of a person's real intent, especially one of a hostile nature.

Since micro-expressions are universal and difficult to falsify, they play a critical role in lie detection and criminal investigations (Metzinger, 2006; Schubert, 2006; Weinberger, 2010). Micro-expression recognition can be employed to detect dangerous demeanors (Metzinger, 2006; Schubert, 2006; Weinberger, 2010; Matsumoto, 2012). Micro-expressions can also be useful in communication and understanding others' intentions in a variety of fields, including business, medicine, law, and national security (Hurly, 2011). Micro-expression detection has broad potential applications ranging from interpreting customer reactions towards various situations and marketing campaigns (Wezowski&Wezowski, 2012) to terrorist attack intercession (Weinberger, 2010). Detection can even be used to predict how likely a person is to abuse their children (Asla, 2012). There are also studies that prove that the ability to recognize micro-expressions depends on the context (Zhang M, et al., 2014) and that we can distinguish emotions not only from the face but also from the whole body language of the person (Proverbio et al., 2014).

There are various micro-expression recognition training tools available, including the Subtle Expression Training Tool (SETT), which teaches users how to study minor expressions, and the Facial Expression Awareness Compassion Emoticons (FACE), which teaches users to recognize the first signs of emotion (Clark et al., 2008; Burrows et al., 2006). One training tool that has traditionally been used to teach micro-expression recognition is the Micro Expression Training Tool (METT) developed and validated by Ekman (2003). The Micro Expressions Training Videos (METV) program is essentially a more elaborate video version of the METT, using video instead of static images. Teaching micro-expression recognition with video has the advantage that the participant is shown the full evolution of each micro-expression. Recognizing micro-expressions within moving stimuli (video) ought to be more difficult than with static stimuli (photos), and should also more closely approximate real life situations. The METV caters for user preferences by including four different test modes—normal, listening speaking and muted modes. We wanted to explore the learning possibilities of the METV, which is a relatively new program that has not previously been the subject of profound study.

The main goal of this research project was to compare the METV with the more established METT. Thus we were comparing a training program based on video with one based on static images. We expected that the METV tests results would correlate with those obtained with METT, but that METV scores would be lower because of the increased difficulty of identifying expressions with moving stimuli. We also expected that individuals who obtained low or high scores on the METT would obtain similarly low or high scores on the METV, and visa-versa. Hence we decided to test the following three hypotheses:

H1: METV test results will correlate with METT test results

H2: Recognizing emotions in videos is more difficult than in still photographs

H3: Individuals scoring low or high on the first test will also score low or high on the second test.

A further goal of the project was to assess the effectiveness of METV as a training tool. As participants continued to use the METV program, we expected that their competence in micro-expression recognition would increase, so that their averaged test scores would be significantly higher than their initial test scores. Moreover, we expected that improvement would correlate with the number of tests completed. We therefore tested hypotheses H4 and H5:

H4: Participants' averaged METV test scores will be higher than their initial test scores

H5: Participants' scores in a particular test mode will positively correlate with the number of tests completed in that mode.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

The METT was obtained from <http://www.ekmaninternational.com/paul-ekman-international-plc-home/training-courses/online-training.aspx/>.

The METV is available online at <http://microexpressions.org/>.

2.2 Participants and study design

2.2.1 Study one

This is a quantitative study in which used a cohort of 62 psychology students (43 females and 19 males; average age: 20 years old) at a large university in Poland. None of the students had previous exposure to micro-expression tools (METT and METV). All the participants completed the METT and METV programs and completed a demographic questionnaire. Participants were assigned randomly to one of two groups. The first group received training and testing in the METT followed by the METV, and the second group received training and testing in the METV followed by the METT. The order of the two measures was reversed in the second group so one program would not influence data for the other program. For research purposes, the subjects were given a subset of 20 of videos from the METV, coded in FACS (www.microexpressions.org). Respondents required about 10 minutes to complete the METV test and about 10 minutes to complete the METT test. Subjects could receive 0 to 100 points on each of the tests as an indicator of their performance in recognizing micro-expressions. Because the emotion recognition scores in both the METT and the METV are based on the same scale (0 to 100), it is possible to directly compare the results from each program using the SPSS analysis.

2.2.2 Study two

The participants in the second study were a large group of people from around the world who registered for a course on micro-expression recognition based on the METV training program. The participants included a variety of people, such as coaches, trainers, business people, and students, who voluntarily registered online at www.microexpressions.org. In all, 2578 persons (1584 female and 1068 male) participated in the study. The mean age of the participants was 35± SD years (age range between 18 and 60 years).

The participants who registered on the METV website were allowed to repeat the METV test as many times as they wanted and could choose to use the different METV test modes (e.g., normal, listening, speaking, test) according to their personal preferences. To estimate the effectiveness of micro-expression training, post-training test scores were compared to pre-training scores.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Control analysis

We performed a control analysis to determine whether the order of program delivery affected performance. The mean scores for each test did not differ significantly, regardless of whether the test was applied first or second (Fig. 1). This indicated that no order effect was present.

3.2 Correlation between METT and METV

The first hypothesis (*H1*) assumed that because the new METV test measures performance in emotion recognition based on micro-expressions, the METV results should correlate with performance in the METT, which is a standard test for emotion recognition based on micro-expressions. The r-Pearson correlation between the METT and METV test results was positively linearly correlated, where $r = 0.442$ and was significant (Table 1). This finding confirms our first hypothesis (*H1*) that micro-expression recognition with the METV program correlates with recognition in the METT program. In addition, the standard deviations (SDs) for the two tests were similar, indicating that the inter-individual disparities in performance were similar for the two programs. The scatter plot in Figure 2 illustrates the variability of the METT–METV correlation across participants.

Table 1. Correlation between METT and METV test scores.

Program	N	Mean	SD	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>
METT	62	61.65	17.39	0.442	< 0.001
METV	62	39.48	17.99	0.442	< 0.001

The mean METV score was significantly lower than the mean METT score (Table 1). This difference confirms the second hypothesis (*H2*) that recognizing emotions in videos (moving stimuli given in the METV) is more difficult than in pictures (static stimuli in the METT). Despite these differences, there is a strong correlation and the SDs are similar (Table 1) for the two programs. This indicates that the METV program is a reliable tool for measuring micro-expression recognition performance and that it can be used alongside the METT program.

Table 2. Relation between the METV and METT test results

Paired Samples Statistics

Pair 1	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
METT	61.6452	62	17.39898	2.20967
METV	39.4839	62	17.99976	2.28597

Paired Samples Correlations			
Pair 1	N	Correlation	Sig.
METT and METV	62	0.442	0.000

Paired Samples Test

Pair 1	Paired Differences					T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
METT and METV	22.16129	18.70758	2.37587	17.41045	26.91213	9.328	61	0.000

The t-test for repeated measurements shows that the difference between the average METT and METV scores is statistically significant. Table 2 shows that the average METT score is significantly higher than the mean METV score (22.16 points difference; $t(61) = 9.328$; $p < 0.0001$). In addition, Cohen's *d* statistic, which measures the size of the effect, shows that the strength of the relationship between the variables METT and METV exceeds 0. Values for Cohen's *d* statistics are characteristically not affected by sample size, which confirms the significance of the result.

Hypothesis *H3* assumed that individuals who exhibited low or high performances on one test would also obtain low or high scores, respectively, on the second test. In order to test this hypothesis, we recoded the METT results on two levels based on the distribution of results; a low METT score was from 0 to 60 and a high METT score was from 60 to 100. We did the same with the METV results; a low METV score was from 0 to 40 and a high METV score was from 40 to 100. The distribution of participants who obtained high versus low scores on the METT and METV tests (Table 3) showed that the majority of those who performed low on the METT also performed low on the METV (21 people, in contrast to 9 who performed high on the METV). Similarly, those who performed high on the METT also performed high on the METV (21 people, in contrast to 11 who performed low on the METV).

Table 3. Cross table of the numbers and percentages of participants with low and/or high METV and METT test results.

METV/METT		Low score	High score	overall
Low scores	N	21	9	30
	%	65.6%	30.0%	48.4%
High scores	N	11	21	32
	%	34.4%	70.0%	51.6%
Overall	N	32	30	62
	%	51.6%	48.4%	100%

The thresholds for low vs. high were 60 points for METT and 40 points for METV based on the average results for each test.

3.3 Effect of METV training on micro-expression recognition

Because the METV is not only a tool for measuring micro-expression recognition performance but also a training tool to improve this ability, the main goal of the second study was to measure the effect of METV training on micro-expression recognition. Consequently, the hypotheses H4 and H5 were tested and results are as discussed below.

3.3.1 Average METV test scores

As shown in Figure 3, the participants' overall average METV test scores (across all tests) were significantly higher than their initial METV test scores, regardless of the test mode. Thus, our hypothesis that the users' initial METV scores would be lower than their performance over time and with training (*H4*) was confirmed. Analogous differences were found for each of the four test modes (normal, listening, speaking, muted), with the highest scores being obtained for the listening test mode and the lowest being obtained for the normal test mode (Figure 3). However, the difference was significant even in the normal test mode. The METV test scores correlated positively with the number of attempts at testing made by the users (Fig. 4). Note the rising trend of METV scores over the testing sequence (Fig. 4). Most of the participants showed improvement within 10 test trials. In general, higher numbers of test trials were associated with higher test scores.

3.3.2 Correlation of METV test scores against number of trials completed

To test *H5*, each of the METV test scores were correlated with the number of testing trials the users had completed (Figs. 4 and 5, Table 4). The "Trial number" variable shows the order in which the subjects did METV trials (attempts). The "No. of trials" variable shows how many times someone participated in the test.

The correlation between the number of trainings and METV performance (post-test) were all positive: $r = 0.32$ for "normal" training, $r = 0.26$ for "listening" training, $r = 0.14$ for "speaking" training, $r = 0.22$ for "test" training, and $r = 0.26$ for "all mode" training. All the correlations were significant; however, not all of them were high. Those results confirmed once more that performance on the METV increased in conjunction with the number of trainings completed by the participants.

Most of the participants showed improvement within 10 test trials (trial numbers). In general, completing more test trials was associated with higher test scores.

3.3.3 Analogous correlations

Analogous correlations were observed across all METV test modes (Table 5). The strongest correlation found was between the number of trials (i.e., whether it was the first, fifth, tenth, etc. attempt at the test) and the score on that individual trial in the testing mode referred to as "test" (described above). Nevertheless, the correlation between the trial number and the individual test scores was strong for all testing modes and for all the testing modes combined (Table 5, left-most data column). In addition, strong correlations were seen for each of the testing modes and for all the testing modes combined when the total number of testing trials completed (in the entire study period) was correlated with the users' average scores over all of their trials

(Table 5, center data column). These data confirm hypothesis *H5*, which posited that there would be a positive correlation between the number of test trials completed in a test mode and the test score achieved for that mode. The relationship between the number of trials conducted and the METV test scores for that trial is shown in Figure 4. The data used to generate the curves in Figure 5 are the same data that were analyzed for the correlational analysis of the trial number multiplied by the individual text score reported in the left-most data column of Table 5. The data were fitted to an increasing trend linear

curve with a very high fit factor.

Table 5. Correlations between METV test performance and indices of experience with METV.

Test mode	Statistic	Individual test trial # vs. score on that trial	Total no. test trials taken by user vs. user's average score (all users)	Total no. test trials taken by user vs. user's average score (serious/studious users)
Normal	Pearson's <i>r</i>	0.290	0.346	0.320
	<i>p</i>	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
	N	608	612	612
Listening	Pearson's <i>r</i>	0.270	0.269	0.261
	<i>p</i>	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
	N	357	359	359
Speaking	Pearson's <i>r</i>	0.306	0.156	0.139
	<i>p</i>	< 0.001	0.012	0.026
	N	250	256	256
Test	Pearson's <i>r</i>	0.451	0.273	0.222
	<i>p</i>	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
	N	1114	1150	1150
All modes combined	Pearson's <i>r</i>	0.352	0.256	0.226
	<i>p</i>	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
	N	2329	2377	2377

3.3.4 Confidence level

The intensity of the participants' program involvement was indexed according to the number of times they chose to take the tests. The participants were divided into four involvement degree subgroups as follows: low (< 3 tests taken), average (3–8 tests taken), serious (9–20 tests taken), and studious (> 20 tests taken). More than three-quarters of the participants in the surveyed group were in the serious or studious subgroups (Fig. 6), which shows a high level of commitment and provides a high degree of confidence in the results.

More than three-quarters of the respondents tested the program more than 9 times. When the correlation analysis for the total number of testing trials completed multiplied by the users' average score was repeated with only serious and studious users, the correlation remained robust for all four testing modes and for all of the testing modes combined (Table 5, far right data column). Of the four testing modes examined, the serious/studious users' performance correlated most strongly with the total number of test trials completed in the normal testing mode. These findings provide additional support for our prediction that using the program more often, as reflected by test trials, would result in better METV test outcomes.

4. Concluding discussion

This century has seen great advances in technological development but also increasing levels of crime,

including issues with national security. It is now more important than ever to be able to detect lies and to judge a person's true intent, and therefore a knowledge of micro-expressions would be an asset to national security and law enforcement personnel. The METV represents an effective tool to train such professionals in micro-expression recognition. Health professionals would also benefit from training with METV, especially considering that patients often withhold information or even give false information. There are currently no published studies investigating the use of micro-expression training with medical professionals (Endres and Laidlaw, 2009), although METT has been used as an adjunct to clinical therapy (Ekman, 2002).

Another set of people who could gain an advantage from improved ability in micro-expression recognition are those involved in sales and marketing. Customer behavior is a notoriously unstable trait, yet with proper training salespeople will be able to find a baseline from which they can study the reactions and behaviors of their clients. Training in micro-expression recognition should assist salespeople to accurately identify and address customer emotional needs. When these emotional needs are met, a salesperson is able to tap into the customer's feelings of confidence and trust (Ekman, 1972; Shiota, et al., 2004; Wiggins, 2005). One avenue for further research would be to assess the effect of METV training on quarterly sales figures. The results from such a study could be extrapolated to many other professional areas, including those in which success is not so easy to measure.

The first part of this research compared the METV program to the previously validated and widely accepted METT. There have been many studies that show METT has a phenomenal success rate in teaching people to accurately recognize micro-expressions (Zhang et al., 2014). The excellent correlation of the test results for the two different programs show that METV could be used instead of the METT or in conjunction with it. Both are computer-based programs. The METV program is a particularly user-friendly method of learning to recognize micro-expressions. This is evidenced by the fact that the majority of the participants in the second study chose to use the program multiple times.

4.1 Conclusion

In the present studies, the METV was confirmed to be a reliable instrument for micro-expression recognition training and testing in relation to the previously established METT program. The confirmation of reliability relative to the METT is further supported by the fact that the two tests had similar SDs. Variations in both tests were very similar; therefore, both the METV and METT tests are shown to filter higher and lower results with high accuracy. Additionally, it was confirmed that users obtained lower scores on the METV than the METT.

One very important result of our study is connected to the possibility of learning to recognize micro-expressions using the METV training program. The data taken from 2578 participants from different countries and different professions showed a correlation between the number of trainings taken and the METV scores. The analysis of test results in relation to the amount of practice revealed a positive correlation between the number of test trials conducted and METV performance. When more tests were taken, better test scores were obtained. In addition, users performed better on all their tests averaged over their whole program experience than they did on their initial tests.

4.2 Recommendation

METV is a relatively new tool and less popular among the various stakeholders. Nevertheless, results from this study show that compared to a well-known tool, METT, it is accurate, and should be adopted to improve efficiency of learning micro-expressions.

Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

References

Asla, N.N., de Paul, J.J., Perez-Albeniz A.A. (2011). Emotion recognition in fathers and mothers at high risk for child physical abuse. *Child Abuse and Neglect* 35, 712-721.

Burrows, A. M., Waller, B. M., Parr, L. A., & Bonar, C. J. (2006). Muscles of facial expression in the chimpanzee (Pan Troglodytes): Descriptive, comparative, and phylogenetic contexts. *J. Anat.*, 208, 153-167

Clark, T., Winkielman P., & McIntosh D. (2008). Autism and the extraction of emotion from briefly presented facial expressions: stumbling at the first step of empathy. *Emotion*, 8, 803-809.

Cole, P.M., Jenkins, P.A., Shott, C.T. (1989). Spontaneous expressive control in blind and sighted children. *Child Dev.* 60, 683-688.

Darwin, C. (1872). *The expression of emotion in man and animals*. New York: Oxford University Press.

Ekman, P. (1972). "Universal and cultural differences in facial expression of emotion", in *Nebraska Symposium on Motivation*. Vol. 19, ed. J. Cole (Lincoln, NE: University of Nebraska Press), 207-283.

Ekman P. (1985). *Telling Lies: Clues to Deceit in the Marketplace, Politics and Marriage*. New York: Oxford University Press.

Ekman, P. (1992). An argument for basic emotions. *Cogn. and Emot.* 6, 169-200.

Ekman, P. (2003). *Emotions Revealed: Recognizing Faces and Feelings to Improve Communication and Emotional Life*. New York: Times Books.

Ekman, P. (2002). *MicroExpression Training Tool (METT)*. University of California, San Francisco. Available from www.emotionsrevealed.com.

Ekman, P. and Friesen, W.V. (1971). Constants across culture in the face and emotion. *J. Personality and Social Psychol.* 17, 124-129.

Ekman, P. and Friesen, W.V. (1978). *Manual for the Facial Action Coding System*. Palo Alto, CA: Consultation Psychologists Press.

Ekman, P. O'Sullivan, M. Friesen, W.V. and Scherer, K.R. (1991). Face, voice and body in detecting deceit. *J. Nonverb. Behav.* 15, 125-135.

Ekman, P. and Rosenberg, E.L. editors (1997). *What the Face Reveals: Basic and Applied Studies of Spontaneous Expression Using the Facial Action Coding System (FACS)*. New York: Oxford University Press.

Ekman, P., Sorenson, E.R. and Freisen, W.V. (1969). Pancultural elements in facial displays of emotion. *Science* 164, 86-88.

Endres, J. and Laidlaw, A. (2009). Microexpression recognition training in medical students: a pilot study. *BMC Medical Education* 9, 1-6.

Haggard, E.A. and Isaacs, K.S. (1966). "Micromomentary facial expressions as indicators of ego mechanisms in psychotherapy", in *Methods of Research in Psychotherapy*, ed. L.A. Gottschalk and A.H. Auerbach (New York: Appleton Century Crofts), 154-165.

Hurley, C.M. (2012). Do you see what I see? Learning to detect micro expressions of emotion. *Motivation and Emotion* 35, 371-381.

Marsh, P.J., Green, M.J., Russel, T.A., McGruire, J., Harris, A. and Coltheart, M. (2010). Remediation of facial emotion recognition in schizophrenia: functional predictors, generalizability, and durability. *Am. J. Psych. Rehab.* 13, 143-170.

Matsumoto, D., Keltner, D., Shiota, M. N., Frank, M. G., & O'Sullivan, M. (2008). "What's in a face? Facial expressions as signals of discrete emotions", in *Handbook of emotions* (New York: Guilford Press), ed. M. Lewis, J. M. Haviland & L. Feldman Barrett, pp. 211-234.

Matsumoto, D. and Hwang, H. (2011). Evidence for training the ability to read microexpressions of emotion. *Motivation and Emotion* 35, 181-191.

Metzinger, T. (2006). Exposing lies. *Scientific American Mind* 17, 32-37. doi:10.1038/scientificamericanmind1006-32.

Proverbio, A.M., Calbi, M., Manfredi, M., and Zani, A. (2014). Comprehending Body Language and Mimics: An ERP and Neuroimaging Study on Italian Actors and Viewers. *PLoS ONE* 9(3):e91294. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.009129.

Schubert, S. (2006). A look tells all. *Scientific American Mind* 17, 26-31. doi:10.1038/scientificamericanmind 1006-26.

Shiota, M. N., Campos, B., & Keltner, D. (2004). "Positive emotion and the regulation of interpersonal relationships", in *The Regulation of Emotion*, ed. P. Philippot & R. S. Feldman (Mahwah: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates).

Tomkins, S.S. (1962). *Affect, Imagery and Consciousness (Vol 1: The Positive Affects)*. New York: Springer.

Tomkins, S.S. (1963). *Affect, Imagery and Consciousness (Vol 2: The Negative Affects)*. New York: Springer.

Weinberger, S. (2010). Airport Security: Intent to Deceive? *Nature* 465, 412-415. doi:10.1038/465412a.

Wezowski, K. and Wezowski, P. (2012). *The Micro Expressions Book for Business*. Antwerp: New Vision.

Wiggins, C. & Lowry, R. (2005). *Negotiation and Settlement Advocacy: A Book of Readings, 2nd ed.* St. Paul: Thompson/West.

Yan, W-J., Wu, Q., Liang, J., Chen, Y-H. and Fu, X. (2013). How fast are the leaked facial expressions: the duration of microexpressions. *J. Nonverb. Behav.*37, 217-230.doi:10.1007/s10919-013-0159-8.

Zhang, M., Fu, Q., Chen, Y-H., and Fu, X. (2014). Emotional context influences micro-expression recognition.PLoS ONE 9(4):e95018. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0095018.

Figures

Figure 1. Comparison of METT and METV test results according to whether each program was administered first or second. In order 1, METT was tested first. In order 2, METV was tested first.

Figure 2. Scatter plot relating METV to METT test results.

Figure 3. Initial versus composite METV tests scores for each of four METV test modes and overall (score %) test results.

Figure 4. Scatter plot illustrating the correlation between METV testperformance and the number of tests conducted (trial numbers).

Figure 5

Figure 5. Mean METV test results in each test mode and overall (Score %) over repeated test trials (linear growth model). The linear fit factor is reported in the graphic (R^2 value).

Figure 6. Distribution amongst groups in Study 2, when participants are grouped according to the number of tests taken.